

A METHOD FOR INDUCING CONTROLLED CRACKS IN CONCRETE AND MEASURING THE EFFICIENCY OF SELF-HEALING AGENTS

Amir Sidiq⁽¹⁾, Syed Adil Amzar Bin Syed Amerruddin⁽²⁾, Rebecca Gravina⁽³⁾, Sujeeva Setunge⁽⁴⁾, Filippo Giustozzi⁽⁵⁾

(1-5) Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology – RMIT University, 376-392 Swanston st., Melbourne, VIC 3000, Australia

ABSTRACT

Durability and mechanical properties of concrete decreases with time due to cracking, resulting in contaminant ingress such as rapid chloride penetration and water particles transferred through these cracks to cause corrosion of the steel in reinforced concrete. The present research presents a method to induce cracking throughout the entire concrete sample's volume homogeneously. By placing a cylindrical concrete sample into an ad-hoc steel mould and applying a compressive loading, confined axial and circumferential pressure is generated that induces controlled cracks in the sample. This procedure is used to induce a specific amount of cracks in the concrete sample hence triggering the repairing action of the self-healing agent. This method overcomes common drawbacks of self-healing efficiency measurements where a single crack is usually being generated by a standard flexural test on beams. X-ray tomography analysis was adopted to calibrate the internal state of damage generated into the sample.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Cracking occurrence in concrete structures is expected at any stage during the life span of the structure typically under tension stresses due to limited tensile characteristics [1]. Due to cracking, the durability and structural capacity of concrete are compromised in an aggressive environment since chlorides and atmospheric water can infiltrates through the cracks and permeate the concrete matrix [2], which will lead to diffusion and enlargement of micro-cracks. Subsequently, corrosion in reinforcement may occur and the risk of failure of the structure increases [3]. To determine the efficiency of self-healing of concrete, research studies tend to develop artificial cracks in cementitious materials. Conventionally, there are limited techniques available for developing cracks in concrete including four-point bending, three-point bending and split tensile testing. Researchers utilise these test methods to determine the onset of cracking and calculate the crack load capacity for a specific concrete material design and then use this experiment to obtain cracks based on their requirements for self-healing. A few studies utilised split test to generate single cracks in their specimens and further test healing efficiency of the mix [4]. Other studies used the three-point bending test to develop single cracks in the mid-span of a concrete beam [5]. However, the majority of

studies on concrete healing use the four-point bending test to initiate cracks [6]. Several methodologies have also been applied to quantify the internal cracking of damaged concrete samples. Researchers utilized non-destructive test methods for crack detection and evaluation, such as ultrasonic methods [7], X-Ray tomography [8], acoustic emission [8] and ground penetrating radar [9]. In this paper an innovative method to induce controlled crack damage in the entire concrete sample was developed. The experiment was conducted by applying various percentage of maximum concrete compressive strength in a specifically-developed steel mould. Measurements before and after sample damaging were taken and comparison related to internal void content, recovery of compressive strength and stiffness were also conducted.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The concrete mix consisted of water to cement, sand to cement and aggregate to cement ratio of 0.54, 1.83 and 2.42, respectively. Target compressive strength of the mix was 30-40 MPa although mechanical resistance was not a main focus of the present study, which was instead intended to develop a procedure to generate controlled damage state inside the samples. Cylindrical samples were casted as per AS 1012.8.1-14 [10] with diameter of 100 mm and height of 200 mm. Samples were demoulded after 24 hours and wet cured for 28 days.

2.1 Steel mould fabrication and illustration

A specific steel mould was developed to obtain a controlled internal damage. The designed mould consisted of two semi-circular sections with side plates connected through bolts. Finite Element analysis was used to determine the appropriate thickness of the mould and bolt strength depending on the concrete ultimate strength. The circumference of the mould was 1% larger than the cylindrical sample (with this value depending on the preliminary FE analysis of stresses and strain as well as to accommodate possible small asperities of the sample after demoulding); the height was designed as to accommodate samples of up to 250 mm. Depending on the height of the sample, circular steel plates could be placed at both ends of the mould to provide uniform compression.

2.2 Sample damaging

Concrete cylindrical samples were removed from the water bath after 28 days and dried for two hours at ambient temperature. Samples were then labelled and measured, and Ultrasonic Velocity Pulse (UPV) test was conducted according to ASTM C597-16 [11] to identify the stiffness of concrete before damaging it. Three samples were tested without any confinement to measure the unconfined compressive strength at failure of concrete after 28 days of curing (e.g. undamaged condition). The remaining samples were then put in the steel mould and incremental loads corresponding to 10%, 15%, 25%, 40%, 55%, 70% and 85% of the maximum strength (unconfined) were applied to generate internal cracking. Four samples were 'damaged' at each loading condition, with one of them being used to evaluate the internal cracking through X-ray testing. UPV measurements were taken after each loading step to obtain the samples' residual stiffness and compressive strength at damaged condition.

2.3 X-Ray Tomography - μ CT scan

In this experiment Bruker Skyscan 1275 X-Ray micro-tomograph was used to determine internal porosity and cracking. Concrete samples with diameter of 55 mm and height of 67 mm were placed on the micro-positioning stage. When the X-ray beam passes through the concrete sample, the intensity is attenuated due to the concrete absorption and the detector receives the residual intensity hence producing the 2D image. At 0.2 degree rotation around its axis and resolution of 1540x1540 a total of 1535 images with thickness of 35 μ m were obtained. Porosity and crack development were further investigated.

3.0 ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

3.1 Internal Damage Evaluation

The X-ray tomography was used to determine the porosity induced in the concrete samples; due to differential compression loading and the ad-hoc fabricated mould, an internal damage state was developed. All samples were analysed by separating the internal air phase (e.g. voids and cracks) from the solid phase (e.g. aggregates and cement mortar) for each 2D image. Material with higher density was observed with lighter grey intensity whereas air pores were dark grey coloured due to less attenuation of the translated intensity [12]. To determine the porosity of various concrete samples and controlled cracks, the optimum of 44-255 grey level threshold was used throughout the entire experiment for consistency of results. Global thresholding algorithm to convert the image to binary from the grey-scale image followed by the application of Otsu's method [13] to further separate the pores and solid phases, were applied during post-processing of x-ray results. The results in Fig. 1 show the porosity of different crack-controlled damages in comparison to undamaged concrete sample (average of 8 undamaged samples). Fig. 2-4 depicts the frequency with respect to sphericity and volume of internal pores at 25% and 85% crack controlled damage in comparison to undamaged samples.

Figure 1: porosity of damaged samples

Figure 2: Frequency of sphericity (A) and bin size (B) of pores for undamaged sample

Figure 3: Frequency of sphericity (A) and bin size (B) of pores for 25% damage

Figure 4: Frequency of sphericity (A) and bin size (B) of pores for 85% damage

3.2 - Compressive strength and stiffness

MTS 1000 kN was used to induce cracks in concrete samples through the steel mould and compressive strength test. After cracks were being induced at different loading levels, concrete samples were tested under ultimate compressive strength to obtain the residual compressive strength after damage. Fig. 5 shows the compressive strength and residual stiffness modulus at various damage levels in comparison to the control mix. Dynamic modulus of elasticity was measured before and after inducing cracks on the same sample through Ultrasonic Velocity Pulse test.

Figure 5: Compressive strength and residual stiffness of concrete after inducing cracking

4.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Compared to common methods that only trigger one single crack (or a few cracks in correspondence to the point of maximum stress), the present approach showed an early possibility to generate cracks of various size and shape inside the entire volume of the sample. The ad-hoc developed steel mould, coupled with X-ray analysis and non-destructive testing, could represent a viable alternative to study the efficiency of healing agents in cementitious materials. The evaluation of the internal damage only based on mechanical testing is in fact a not fully reliable method as depicted in Fig. 5; results showed great variability and very small differences were noticed among different damage levels. The application of loading rates between 10% and 55% proved to generate very small cracking patterns with these being not easy to capture by the X-ray machine; thin capillary cracking (e.g. less than 10-30 μm) can be overlooked due to the equipment resolution. UPV testing was able to capture small variations in stiffness (Fig. 5) before and after damage although variability was slightly high.

Internal porosity was evaluated according to its overall magnitude but also through the study of the distribution of shape and volume of the cracks. From Fig. 2-4, one can observe that the sphericity of the cracks is very close to 1 (perfect sphere) in undamaged samples – bottom right of the graph – and moves to the upper left area of the graph with increasing damage intensity. Sphericity tends to shift from a value of 1 to 0.5 (and lower) thus indicating the change in shape of internal voids due to the formation of the cracks and their geometrical inconsistency. The distribution of the volume of internal voids also follows a clear trend where a greater damage (e.g. 85%) corresponds to bigger voids and the shifting of the volume distribution towards the right side of the histogram scale.

As general representation of results, Fig. 6 shows the 3D visualization of three concrete samples under X-ray at undamaged, 25% and 85% damage conditions.

(A) undamaged sample (B) 25% damage (C) 85% damage

Figure 6: 3D visualization of undamaged sample compared to 25% and 85% damage

Based on the results, the fabricated steel mould for developing internal cracks in concrete cylindrical specimens showed to be a viable alternative to generate cracking patterns inside the sample overcoming common approaches that only simulate single cracks, or a group of cracks in a small specific area of the sample. With proper calibration of the external load to be applied to the sample, the size, shape and volume of the cracks can be modified. Healing agents could achieve different results depending on size and density of the cracks to be filled.

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